

POSSIBILITY OF SEPARATION OF COPPER AND SILVER ZONES IN AN ALLOY OF COPPER AND SILVER BY ZINC, CHROMATOGRAPHICALLY

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It is found that the chromatographic order Cu-Ag-Zn with alumina as adsorbent is reversed in dilute solutions to Cu-Zn-Ag. This is shown to be due to the preferential adsorption of Zn⁺⁺ over the Ag⁺ in dilute solutions. It is suggested that this method may be used to separate and estimate the Cu-Ag alloys

Schwab and Jokers (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1937, 50, 546) describe Cu⁺⁺-Ag⁺-Zn⁺⁺ as the order of chromatographic adsorption from top to bottom in a column of alumina, from solutions of mixed ions. With the developer ammonium sulphide, copper gives a dark colour and silver, a dark grey zone. Estimation of copper-silver alloys is not good by this process since the two zones are not well marked. It is necessary to separate the two zones by interposition with another of different colour, possibly white. During

FIG. 1

our experiments on the estimation of brass by chromatographic method (this *Journal*, 1949, 26, 415) attempts were made to separate the copper and zinc zones by the interposition of different ions. While confirming the work of these authors it was found that the chromatographic order was sometimes reversed and we obtained $\text{Cu}^{++} - \text{Zn}^{++} - \text{Ag}^+$ as the order of separation. The chromatogram Cu-Zn-Ag (black-white-grey), developed by ammonium sulphide, saturated with hydrogen sulphide, was uniform and the lines of separation were quite sharp and horizontal. The previous authors worked with solutions of M and $M/10$ only. In our experiments the concentrations of solutions were from $N/25$ to $N/200$. This reversal is perhaps due to the preferential adsorption of the Zn^{++} ions over that of Ag^+ ions at lower concentrations. Experiments were therefore undertaken on the adsorption of silver and zinc ions from their respective salt solutions at different concentrations.

The methods of setting up of the column and working are exactly the same as in the previous paper. Fig. 1 shows the chromatograms mentioned in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Adsorption of Ag^+ and Zn^{++} on Alumina: Silver Nitrate.—Alumina (3 g.), described in the previous paper, was placed in each of five bottles of 30 c.c. capacity. Silver nitrate solutions (15 c.c.) of strength $N/10$, $N/20$, $N/40$, $N/80$, $N/160$ were added respectively to each of the bottles. The bottles were closed and shaken; they were kept overnight at the laboratory temperature in a thermostat. The strength of the solutions after adsorption was determined by titration against sodium chloride of known strength. The weight of the silver ion adsorbed per g. of the adsorbent was calculated.

Zinc Sulphate.—Similarly the adsorption from zinc sulphate ($\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$) from solutions of different concentrations was determined as above. The zinc was estimated by titration with potassium ferrocyanide using diphenylamine as an indicator. The data are given in the following table.

TABLE I

Strength of solution.			Strength of solution		
Before adsorption.	After adsorption.	$\frac{\text{Amt. of ion adsorbed}}{\text{Wt. of adsorbent}}$	Before adsorption.	After adsorption.	$\frac{\text{Amt. to ion adsorbed}}{\text{Wt. of adsorbent}}$
Silver nitrate.			Zinc sulphate.		
1.021N/10	0.357N/10	0.036	2.13N/10	1.61N/10	0.017
0.511	0.295	0.012	1.06	0.58	0.016
0.256	0.165	0.005	0.53	0.21	0.011
0.128	0.076	0.003	0.27	0.06	0.007
0.064	0.014	0.003			

In Fig. 2, the amounts of ion (+) adsorbed per gram of alumina are plotted against initial ionic concentrations of respective solutions. It is seen that at lower concentrations there is a greater adsorption of zinc ions per g. of the adsorbent than the

silver ions, while at higher concentrations more of silver is adsorbed than zinc. Therefore the preferential adsorption of zinc over silver at lower concentrations is responsible for the reversal of the chromatographic order.

FIG. 2

The results are only qualitative but this suggests a method of separating copper and silver and estimating them in an alloy of copper and silver. Otherwise Cu-Ag with ammonium sulphide give more or less similarly coloured bands and the line of separation is not very clear.

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